

KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE OF PARENTS REGARDING AIRWAY CLEARANCE OF AN INFANT

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Abstract

Background: Infections of the respiratory tract of an infant are most common and a very serious complication. The rate of pulmonary infection is about 60.84 percent in developing countries. The main target of the airway clearance is to assist the individual in discharging the secretions, either it is by physical or mechanical because it reduces the rate of complications which is caused by retention of the secretions.

Objective: To determine the knowledge and attitude of parents regarding airway clearance of an infant.

Methodology: A cross-sectional survey was done from April 2025 to September 2025 in Karachi on Parents of one or more than one child. The sample size was 377, and the non-probability convenience sampling was used. Data was evaluated through a self-administered questionnaire, and analysis of data was done through SPSS version 23.0.

Result: A total of 377 research participants were included in this study. The results showed that the knowledge of airway clearance was limited to around 257 (68.16%) respondents replying no. About 163 (43.23%) research participants used medicines for their child's treatment. About 214 (56.76%) research participants were used to treat their child through physical therapy treatment.

Conclusion: The knowledge of airway clearance was limited among the parents of infants, while most of the parents used physical therapy treatment for airway clearance in the hospitals.

INTRODUCTION

It is a set of techniques that helps the mucus to move from the lungs and makes it easier to cough up, and improves the functions of the lungs called airway clearance. [1] Aerosol clearance decreases the infection rate of the lungs and enhances lung

function. It is important because it helps to prevent the thick mucus from developing and blocking the distal airways. [2] The main target of the airway clearance is to assist the individual in discharging the secretions, either it is by physical or mechanical

because it reduces the rate of complications which is caused by retention of the secretions. [3] The reason for airway clearance is necessary for the individual because it causes apnea, fluctuations in heart rate, disturbances of mucous layers, alterations in blood gases, impaired lung functions, increases the intensity of pain, and alters cerebral oxygenation. [4] Basically, airway clearance is necessary to remove the obstructions of the airways, and the obstruction means the mucus, any abnormal growths, injuries, burns, swelling, or foreign particles that block the airways. [5] Airway obstruction can occur over time or under certain circumstances. An individual feels having difficulty in taking breath may be something stuck in the windpipe or a reaction to allergies. These obstructions need to be cleared from the airway of an individual. [6] There are many symptoms of airway blockage, like: problems in breathing or speaking, hearing different noises while a person takes breath, like wheezing or stridorous sounds, shortness of breath, changes in facial skin color, like a person looks bluish in color or cyanosed, etc. [7]

Infections of the respiratory tract of an infant are most common and a very serious complication. The rate of pulmonary infection is about 60.84 percent in developing countries. [8] There are many ways to treat respiratory infections and reduce airway issues. The treatment of airway clearance is through medicines, nebulizers, or physical therapy. [9] When an individual is treated with medicines, the consultant gives some medications that can cause the mucus to thin, and the patient can easily expectorate the mucus. In some cases consultant uses bronchodilators, which dilate the bronchi. It works as a muscle relaxant in the airways. The relaxation causes the airways to open easily. [10] There are three main types of bronchodilators: beta 2-agonists, anticholinergics, and theophylline. Some consultants choose corticosteroids to treat the airway clearance issues. [11] On the other hand consultant refers the patient to the physical therapist to perform different physical therapy strategies to remove the secretions from the lungs. [12] Physical therapy helps the patient reduce chest infections or remove the secretions. Physical therapists have many options to treat respiratory or airway clearance issues. Physical therapist uses chest percussions, which can be

manual or mechanical percussions, or use the acapella instrument to enhance the airway activity, or sometimes physical therapists use suctioning to remove the mucus from the lungs. [13]

Consultants and physical therapists have many options to treat the airway issues. But sometimes they face many problems from the patient's attendant or parents. Parents thought that these approaches would harm their child or cause more pain to their child. [14] Some parents are educated, or they relate to the healthcare professionals, so they can understand the procedures, and they can cooperate with the physical therapist, but in some cases, parents cannot cooperate with the doctors or physical therapist. [15] Our study aims to evaluate the knowledge and attitude of parents regarding the airway clearance of an infant.

METHODOLOGY

It was a cross-sectional study conducted from April 2025 to September 2025 in Karachi. The research participants were chosen through a non-probability convenience sampling. Parents of one or more than one child in Karachi were recruited, and a sample size of 377 was calculated through Raosoft.com software. Inclusion criteria: parents whose child is admitted to hospital for treatment of any medical condition, both male and female, age group from less than 30 years to more than and equal to 50 years, both literate and illiterate, parents related to health profession or not, no of children between one and more than 5. The exclusion criteria were parents whose children are not admitted to the hospital due to illness or any infection, and those parents who were not willing to participate in our study were excluded. In this study, we used a self-administered questionnaire. Data were analyzed by SPSS version 23.0 software.

RESULT

The 377 research participants were recruited for this study. The demographic data of the research participants were discussed in this paragraph. The variables included of the participants was gender like 256 (67.90%) was female and 121 (32.09%) was male participants, the age of the participants we selected for the study were less than 30 years to more or equal than 50 years, the education, occupation,

the number of children’s around 158 (41.9%) had more than five children’s as shown in Table no.1:

TABLE NO:1 DEMOGRAPHIC DATA OF RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS

S.No.	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Gender		
	Father	121	32.09%
	Mother	256	67.90%
2	Age		
	<30 years	139	36.87%
	30-39 years	127	33.68%
	40-49 years	76	20.15%
	≥50 years	35	9.28%
3	Education		
	Literate	175	46.41%
	Illiterate	202	53.58%
4	Occupation		
	Healthcare Professional	129	34.21%
	Non-Healthcare Professional	248	65.7%
5	No.of Children		
	1-2	96	25.46%
	3-4	123	32.62%
	>5	158	41.9%
6	Age of the youngest child		
	<1 year	108	28.64%
	1-5 years	126	33.42%
	>5 years	143	37.93%

When asked about the knowledge of airway clearance, around 257 (68.16%) replied no, that they don’t know airway clearance. When asked the question whether they knew about the breathing issues, about 294 (77.98%) said yes.

When asked from the research participants about the symptoms that worsen the infant’s condition, the replied no around 201 (53.31%). When asked the questions regarding treatment or feels anxious then 229(60.74%) responded yes and 148(39.25%) responded no as shown in Table no.2:

TABLE NO.2: KNOWLEDGE AND ATTITUDE OF PARENTS

S.No.	Questions related to the knowledge and attitude of participants	Frequency (%)
1	Do you know about the airway clearance?	
	Yes	120 (31.83%)
	No	257 (68.16%)
2	Does your child ever face a breathing problem?	
	Yes	294 (77.98%)
	No	83 (22.01%)

3	Do you know about the symptoms that indicate that your child's condition is getting worse? Yes No	176 (46.68%) 201 (53.31%)
4	Do you know when your child needs the treatment of airway clearance? Yes No	114 (30.02%) 263 (69.76%)
5	Do you think that the treatment of airway clearance can cause more stress than they are worth? Yes No	229 (60.74%) 148 (39.25%)

When asked the 377 research participants about the airway clearance treatment, some of the research participants said they treated their child through medicines, or some said they treated their child through physical therapy.

Around 163 (43.23%) research participants said their child was treated with medicines. Around 51 (13.52%) treated by bronchodilators, 44 (11.67%) treated through mucolytic, 41 (10.87%) by corticosteroids, and around 27 (7.16%) treated with anticholinergic agents, as shown in Figure no.1:

FIGURE NO: 1 MEDICAL TREATMENT OF AIRWAY CLEARANCE

Around 214 (56.76%) research participants replied that their infant was treated through physical therapy.

About 41 (10.87%) participants replied that their infant was treated by mechanical percussions, around 76 (20.15%) participants responded that their child was treated through manual percussions.

Around 23 (6.1%) participants responded that their child was treated through the use of an acapella.

Around 41 (10.87%) research participants said that their infant cleared their airway issues by doing breathing exercises.

Around 33 (8.75%) replied that their child was treated through suctioning, as shown in Figure no.2:

FIGURE NO: 2 PHYSICAL THERAPY TREATMENT OF AIRWAY CLEARANCE

DISCUSSION

The thermoregulation mechanism in healthcare settings to maintain healthy breathing can be affected in neuro-genetic disorders.[16] There are some factors that cause the worsening of the patient's health and may lead to death: the conditions that cause damage to the function of cilia in the lung, impairing the airway clearance by causing retention and aggregation, which gives the opportunity for bacteria to make colonies and causes inflammation.[17] The knowledge and attitude of parents play a vital role in the care of their infected child, and they should also have insight understanding of the condition to supervise the management of staff towards their child. Because good nursing care can provide good outcomes. [18] The aim of the study is to determine the knowledge and attitude of parents regarding airway clearance of an infant.

Around 67.90% research participants were mothers, which showed that the mothers are more concerned for the health of their child. Similarly, a study reported that the health maintenance of a child is always present as a threat to the mothers in daily life. As they thought that their child was more prone to infections and other illnesses as compared to others and due to this reason they behave very consciously during the routine activities of their child.[19]

In our study, there were 36.87% research participants were less than 30 years old, which showed that more parents at a younger age are more prone to having their child's airway and breathing issues. Additionally, a study conducted in Saudi Arabia reported, the knowledge of parents regarding disease prevention was limited, especially fathers had less understanding as compared to mothers in the multiple aspects of their child's health that need to be better by enhancing the knowledge of parents to improve the health status of a child. [20]

According to the World Health Organization, knowledge is the basis of any person, and it helps to make one's belief system.[21]

So, the results of our study showed: knowledge of parents regarding airway clearance is limited, i.e., 68.16%. Furthermore, the guidelines of the WHO are necessary to increase the quality of life of both maternal and child health. Many countries around the world need effective implementation of WHO

guidelines, and it can be accomplished by the provision of learning facilities to the general public through seminars, workshops, and hands-on training sessions that can promote the professional development of education and enhance the quality and safety of the public. [22]

Through our study results, it was clearly observed that the question about the knowledge of the breathing issues of infants among the parents was fine enough, i.e.77.98%. Similarly, a study reported that, majority of the parents know the aspiration for their child, while some have insufficient understanding regarding the process of aspiration among children. [23]

In the present study, Parents of an infant choose physical therapy more instead of medical treatment for the airway clearance of their infant, about 56.76% while others use medicines for the treatment of their infant's respiratory health. This shows the importance of physical therapy interventions and their preferences. A study revealed the collaborative characteristics of physical therapy in infants, which especially connected the caregivers, parents, and healthcare providers. It also specifies the evidence-based practice that enhances pediatric physical therapy and improves the quality of life for children. [24]

CONCLUSION

The knowledge regarding the airway clearance was observed to be limited among parents of infants, while most of the parents used physical therapy treatment for airway clearance in the hospitals, and used medicines less for the treatment of their child. The reason behind the choice of physical therapy instead of medical treatment was the possible adverse effects after the use of medicines are more likely than with the use of physical therapy interventions. And therefore, doctors also prescribe physical therapy treatment to ensure better care of an infant without giving harm to them.

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